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BEHAVIOURAL STUDIES OF *BOLEOPHTHALMUS DUSSUMIERI* (VAL., 1837) ON THE SILTED INTERTIDAL MUDFLATS OF ULHAS RIVER ESTUARY

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ABSTRACT

Ulhas River Estuary (URE) sediment is highly silted. *Boleophthalmus dussumieri* (Val., 1837) is a mudskipper species of a common occurrence on the intertidal mudflats developed on either banks of URE. The present study recorded the various activities like burrow construction, feeding, territoriality and courtship, of *B. dussumieri* using scan and focal sampling method on the surface during tidal movements on the exposed mudflats of URE near Kolshet creek. Although the breeding and territoriality of *B. dussumieri* being normal, the other behavioral activities such as courtship, construction of burrows and survivorship were different as compared to the earlier observations by various experts. Breeding pairs preferred to develop burrows at spring tide limits. Burrows lacked chimneys and pit-pools. Juveniles remained without burrows and were found to secure position by penetration in loose soil during flood tide. Feeding on muddy surface was performed by strange straining behaviour.

Keywords: *Boleophthalmus dussumieri*, mudskipper, tidal oscillation, Ulhas river estuary, courtship, territoriality, feeding behavior, breeding behaviour, courtship, burrows, mudflats, siltation, silt, pollution, soil texture.

INTRODUCTION

i. Mudskippers are well-known for their amphibious and benthofossorial habit often found for courtship and feeding vigorously on the exposed mud flats of coastal waters (Clayton, 1993). Ishimatsu and Graham (2011) recorded that mudskippers burrows are highly variable in structures even within a species. They were recorded as biological indicators for environmental monitoring of coastal marine waters (Ansari, et al., 2014). Ikebe and Oishi (1996) correlated environmental parameters with behaviour of *Periophthalmus modestus*. Ulhas River estuary (URE) is located in the vicinity of Thane City near Mumbai, Maharashtra State, India. URE is well known for its rich and diverse fisheries from decades supporting a considerable fishermen population of the area. Mudskipper fishery is highly popular since it was earlier supported by three important species viz. *Boleophthalmus dussumieri* (Val., 1837), *Boleophthalmus boddarti* (Pallas, 1770) and *Taenioides cirratus* (Blyth, 1860) locally known as 'niwati', 'chitti' and 'waati' respectively (Rathod, 2005).

B. dussumieri is abundant species of mudskipper inhabiting on the intertidal mudflats of Ulhas River estuary (URE). *B. dussumieri* contribute to one of the important and highly priced fishery species along URE. *B. dussumieri* has been studied considerably from URE for its breeding and feeding behaviour (Mutsaddi and Bal, 1973; Rathod and Patil, 2009). They maintain the burrows and exhibit intense territoriality on the mudflats of URE (Mutsaddi and Bal, 1973; Rathod, 2005). Their burrows are often open with slight elevation, sort of chimney and are located in the tiny pit-pools constructed of earth to retain water during low tide. They keep their tail immersed in this water for moistening their body surface so as to expedite the respiration through skin when they are exposed to air (Mutsaddi and Bal, 1973; Clayton, 1993; Yee, 1996).

Fig-1: Satellite images of the Ulhas River estuary and Sampling Station

Ulhas River Estuary showing locations of three soil sampling stations-1, 2 & 3 at upper, middle and lower reaches respectively. Kolshet Creek (station 1) located near Thane City of Maharashtra State in India, between Latitude 19.228794N and Longitude 72.982963E on the world map showing the study station where *B. dussumieri* on the mudflats are of common site.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

- ii. **Study area:** Bimonthly observations of various behavioral patterns of *B. dussumieri* and monthly sediment sampling were carried out. The ambient specimens were observed at ‘Kolshet’ creek station ‘1’ situated in the upper stretch of the Ulhas river estuary, lying between latitude 19°14’49”N and longitude 72°59’50” E from the months of November 2015 through April 2016 to record various behavioral activities like feeding, territoriality, construction of burrows, courtship, and survivorship on the exposed mudflats of approx. 100 sq. m (10 m x10 m) area of Ulhas River estuary (Fig.1). Soil samples on monthly basis were collected from three stations from mudflats along (1) head of the estuary near study area at Kolshet creek (2) from middle region 7.8 km away from station 1 at Versova bridge and (3) from downstream of the estuary nearly 13.6 km away from station 1 at Ghodbunder sand landing centre (Fig. 1).
- iii. **Analysis of silt:** Silt was analyzed using Buchanan’s pipette method (1984).
- iv. **Behavioural Study:** The behavioral observation of the *B. dussumieri* was accomplished using *scan and focal sampling* method (Altmann 1974; Bowden *et al.* 2008 and Gilby *et al.* 2010) during the low tide at the foresaid study station for a period of four months (Fig.1). Diminutive behavioral patterns were recorded with help of ‘Sony’ Handy-cam (a movie-cum-photography camera) model: HDR-CX130E, to produce appropriate images and videos. The videos were used to support and revise the observations recorded on field. In present study, four aspects were ordained to understand the behaviour of the *B. dussumieri* on the selected mudflat during the present study viz. (1) siltation and its impact on the burrowing behaviour of the mudskipper; (2) feeding behaviour and (3) territoriality and courtship behaviour.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

i. Siltation and its impact on the burrowing behaviour

Siltation was profound in URE towards mouth and middle region with 47.92% and 45.99% silt respectively, on an average of 46.95%, during present study. This is probably pertaining to the higher sand-dredging activities in the middle and lower regions during the study period. However, the siltation was near 31.26% at head of the estuary (Fig 2). Although the station 1 showed comparatively low silt percentage the silt above 30% is considered as disturbed condition (Hossain *et al.*, 2014). According to Rathod (2016), overall the sediment structure of URE was **clay to silty-clay type** (Fig. 3).

According to some experts, normally the burrows of *B. dussumieri* are guarded by a pit-pool to retain water around the orifice in which the individual immerses its tail to keep body wet for the purpose of cutaneous respiration (Clayton, 1993; Al-Behbehani and Ebrahim, 2010). Also the burrow orifice is elevated in a conical mound of mud like a chimney. However, in present study the burrows of *B. dussumieri* developed on the mudflats of near Kolshet creek (sampling station) did not have any ‘chimney’, as such or the pit-pool. Probably it was not possible due to high siltation which decreases the loamy nature of the soil not sufficient to render consistency to build pits. In such cases the individuals instead, remained in the vicinity of tiny water streams occurred on the surfaces or available natural pits for moistening their skin, required for respiration (Fig. 4-i). Individuals were also found otherwise, to roll on the wet soil for moistening their skin to ensure the cutaneous respiration (Fig. 4-iii).

It has been observed that the present siltation hindered the construction of burrows which probably affected the successful breeding of the *B. dussumieri* in the ambient water body. Consequently, the mature individuals in the study area were found to confine their burrows to upper intertidal limits (above the line of daily tidal levels which occasionally covered during spring tide only) during the study period (Fig. 4-ii). This might be for securing the burrow from getting demolished by tidal current. This kind of adaptation in mudskippers discerned that this helped them to attain breeding between the two subsequent spring tides.

Fig. 4: General behaviour of individuals after exposure of their burrows.

<p>ii. Burrows distant from the daily tidal lines.</p>	
<p>iii. Rolling behaviour for skin moistening</p>	<p>i. Pit-pool filled with water during low tide often used as source of water for respiration and feeding. The water was however used after every feeding attempt probably for winnowing the diatom.</p> <p>ii. Mature individuals developed burrows distant from the daily tidal (upper intertidal) lines perhaps to get the firm substratum for courtship activities and secured burrows.</p> <p>iii. Mature individuals were found rolling on the moist ground to ensure skin moistening as their burrows built on extra tidal limits and hence lacked water.</p>

Young ones of *B. dussumieri* possessed no burrows and were observed penetrating into the loose soil during high tide inundations. This might be helping them to avoid from getting swiped away due to tidal currents from their home area. It was of common sight that nearly 3-4 hours of exposure of mudflat during low-tide rendered the surface harder. This made difficult for young-ones to penetrate their body in the loose soil beneath. To cope up with this difficulty they were observed to fetch water in mouth from the available nearby pits and apply it on the hardened surface smartly to soften it before they wriggled their body downwards. This activity also attributes to the siltation in the region which hindered the construction of burrows.

ii. Feeding Behaviour

B. dussumieri are known for surficial feeding on diatoms (Mutsaddi and Bal, 1969; Rathod and Patil, 2009;). Feeding was performed by swinging head keeping mouth wide open close to hardened ground wiping the surface to collect food (Fig. 5-i). Juveniles collected food from wet soil and were observed to visit available pits to clean the same by straining action.

Fig-5: Feeding behaviour: Surficial head swiping and straining behaviour

<p>ii. Winnowing behaviour</p> <p>i. Side-to-side swinging of head while feeding. The individual touches to surface with mouth open-wide produced into funnel of lips and swipe its head side to side collecting diatoms.</p> <p>ii. Frequent visit to water for winnowing the diatoms in mouth.</p>	
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iii. Territoriality and Courtship Behaviour

According to Mutsaddi and Bal (1970) the reproductive cycle of *Boleophthalmus dussumieri* from Bombay (19°N) revealed the period of active maturation (gonadal stages IV—VI) lasted from February to May in males and March to June in females and the fish spawn once a year over the period July to September. This corroborates with the population included more of younger individuals of *B. dussumieri* during the month of November in present study. Specimens were found in fully mature condition towards the month of January to February. Likewise, the sexual pairing occurred during the latter part of the study period i.e. in the month of February to March. Pairing of the individuals occurred very frequently during the month of February, in present study. During courtship, the individuals were restricting themselves very close to their burrows to ensure the escape from threat. Usually there were two entrances (openings) on a single burrow on an average distance of 1.5 feet which were little different in size, one was smaller than the other. Although both male and female resided in same burrow however, the males preferred the one which was bigger opening and female, the smaller. Males were dominant and possessive of females; males did not allow female to stray away from the burrow and forced them to remain in confinement by frequent chasing.

Fig. 6: Breeding habit: Territoriality and courtship behaviour

<p>i. Equidistance territories</p>	<p>ii. Alert and vigilant individual protecting its burrow in exposed condition during low tide.</p>
	<p>A. Nests are built at a regular distance from each other to form equidistance territories which are vigorously protected from neighbours.</p> <p>B. Alert and vigilant individual protecting its burrow in exposed condition during low tide.</p> <p>C. Mates of opposite sex have separate openings of same burrow. Male uses bigger opening while female, the smaller. Males often try to push female in the burrow to avoid her from eloping.</p>
<p>iii. Mates build separate openings of burrow in the neighborhood.</p>	

CONCLUSION

B. dussumieri is highly adapted to the present conditions. Adult *B. dussumieri* were unable to build chimneys and pit-pools around their burrows due to the highly silted soil of ambient mudflats. They preferred peripheral hardened mudflats which were inundated during spring tides. Siltation probably hindered the breeding. However, the individuals who developed burrows at spring tide limits involved courtship actively. Dominant male forced female in confinement. Although male and female both remained in same burrow they used separate (personal) openings for exit and entry. Juveniles remained without burrows and were found to penetrating in mud during high tide, using water for softening the dried surface, to secure position.

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